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Guidelines to Improve Effectiveness of Educational Institution Administration by Using Transformational Leadership of Administrators, Thailand

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Abstract

Today's global society is full of advancement from the development of high-level technology. The study results shall be used as a guideline for developing educational institution administration to become stable and sustainable learning organizations in the future. This research aimed 1) to study levels of transformational leadership among administrators of private schools, 2) to study levels of effectiveness of educational institution administration among administrators of private schools 3) to study transformational leadership that affects effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools and 4) to study a guideline to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership among administrators of private schools. The research was conducted on the basis of survey research design. The sample comprised 266 teachers of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office. Key informants were 5 school administrators. The research results indicated as follows: 1) Overall and each aspect of transformational leadership among administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office were at a high level, 2) Overall and each aspect of effectiveness of educational institution administration were at a high level, 3) Transformational leadership among administrators affected effectiveness of educational institution administration among administrators of private schools with the statistical significance level of 0.05, the multiple correlation coefficient was 87.80%, 4) Guidelines to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership can be summarized as follows: 4.1) Elements of transformational leadership that could be used to improve the effectiveness were intellectual stimulation and idealized influence, 4.2) Effectiveness of educational institution administration required strategic planning with PDCA, proactive policies, and advanced technology.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Effectiveness of Educational Institution Administration

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

Today's global society is full of advancement from the development of high-level technology. It is a great revolution of humankind, entering into globalization. There are changes in economic, social, and political structures, encouraging countries across the world need to depend on each other. The big world seems to be smaller. Distant areas can get in touch in a split second. Everyone enters into a united society. Technologies are advanced. Globalization or borderless world grows much faster, becomes more intense, continuous, complicated and related to each other, caused by technological advancement in each field, such as science, engineering, computer, communication and telecommunication. Innovation and technologies including social advancement have changed tremendously (Nattapan Kaejornnan. 2008: 12-13).

Educational management in accordance with National Education Act B.E. 2542 (1999) and amended by the National Education Act (No.2) B.E. 2545 (2002) and the National Education Act (No.3) B.E. 2553 (2010), Section 43, was prescribed that an administration and provision of education by private sector shall have freedom with a supervision, monitoring, and quality and educational standard evaluation from the State, and shall perform in accordance with the criteria on quality and educational standard evaluation similar to that of a public establishment of education (Office of the Basic Education Commission, 2014).

Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office was established from the order of the National Council for Peace and Order (NCPO) number 19/2560 on reform steering in regional education and administration of the Ministry of Education, dated on 3 April 2017, item 11 – a provincial education office under Office of the Permanent Secretary for Education should be established to carry out the mission of Ministry of Education in relation to educational administration and management as prescribed by law, performing public services in accordance with duties, policies, and strategies of government agencies as assigned while duties and authorities in provincial areas are given (Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, online, 2022). It was said that problems and obstacles in administration and management came from a lack of public relations, a lack of participation, and a lack of integration of each group in giving cooperation on activity management.

School effectiveness is generated from the state of society, atmosphere, and environment surrounding students that shall support learning properly, including readiness of resources, documents, instructional media, materials, equipment, suitable technologies with good quality and efficiency, adequate budgets and human resources to ensure educational management shall be efficient and able to develop students to become learning persons who have better quality of life, see the value and importance of preserving natural resources and environment, live in changing society happily, contributing to stable and sustainable country development. The components of school effectiveness are formal organization in which external relationship and organizational internal process must be managed to be consistent with conditions of social education process. School system refers to learning achievement, efficient allocation of resources, adaptability to internal and external environment, and ability to create teachers' job satisfaction (Pimpan Suriyo, 2009: 27). This is consistent with the concept of Hoy and Ferguson (Hoy and Ferguson, 1985) stating that the components of the effectiveness of educational institutions are eagerness to learn, passion for reading, students' motivation to seek knowledge, teachers' job satisfaction, teachers' ability in using media, innovation, and technologies, ability to manage resources efficiently, and adaptability to internal and external environment. Robbins (Robbins. 2001:42) stated that educational institution administrators with transformational leadership were more likely to manage education in their educational institutions to achieve efficiency and effectiveness according to the set goals. One of important factors for success or failure is leaders of those organizations or educational institutions. Educational institutions play the most vital role in putting a policy into practice to achieve the determined objectives or the set goals, being able to manage education to people thoroughly and equally. The operations to enable educational institutions to have success and maximum benefits depend on various factors, such as good management, effective management in educational institutions, and using resources acquired wisely (Saman Asawapoom. 2006: 23). With regard to educational institution administration, leaders play a huge role in developing the organization to achieve effectiveness and efficiency with positive changes. Therefore, administrators need to have systematic change management for school

administration. Transformational leader is a process that influences how to change attitude at work to ensure education shall meet quality. Transformational leadership is popular nowadays as it satisfies and has an influence on followers. Therefore, it is necessary that administrators and teachers need paradigm shift, vision at work according to the theory of Bass and Avolio (Bass and Avolio, 1994) mentioning transformational leadership that it can be seen from leaders who stimulate and inspire all workers and followers to be aware of mission and vision. Based on the above reasons, the researcher was interested in studying a guideline to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, based on transformational leadership theory of Bass and Avolio (Bass and Avolio, 1994) and the theory of Hoy and Ferguson (Hoy and Ferguson, 1985) that affect effectiveness of educational management. The study results shall be used as a guideline for developing educational institution administration to become stable and sustainable learning organizations in the future. Why is this problem important?

1.2 State Hypotheses and Their Correspondence to Research Design

1. Transformational leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office is at a high level.
2. Effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office is at a high level.
3. Transformational leadership of administrators has an effect on effectiveness of educational institution administration of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office with statistical significance.

2. Method

2.1 Research conceptual framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

2.2 Research methodology

The research on a guideline to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office

was conducted on survey research design that combines quantitative research and qualitative research. The research was conducted according to the following:

2.3 Population and sample

Population in the research included 858 teachers from 23 private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office of the academic year 2022 (Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, 2022).

The sample comprised 266 teachers from 23 schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office of the academic year 2022 (Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, 2022). Krejcie and Morgan's table (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970: 607-610) was used to determine the sample size and the sample was selected by stratified random sampling based on the size of schools, followed by simple random sampling.

2.4 Key informants

Key informants about a guideline to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, selected by purposive sampling method, consisted of 5 administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, who received management awards or transformational leadership awards.

2.5 Research instruments

2.5.1. Quantitative research

The instrument was a questionnaire about 1) general information of questionnaire respondents. It is a checklist questionnaire consisting of genders, ages, education levels, levels of classrooms, and teaching experience, 2) opinion about transformational leadership of administrators, 3) opinion about effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, in the form of 5-point rating scale (Likert, 1976:247) and open ended questions about problem status and suggestion about transformational leadership and effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office.

2.5.2. Qualitative research

The instrument used for data collection was a structured interview. The interview framework was determined from a point obtained from the questionnaire that teachers viewed that the development should be given to intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, individualized consideration, and idealized influence so as to find out a guideline to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office.

2.6 Data analysis

Part 1 – Frequency distribution of marital status of the respondents were performed and percentage was calculated, and presented in the form of tables and text.

Part 2 – Levels of transformational leadership of administrators were analyzed mean () and standard deviation (S.D.). The analysis results obtained were interpreted by item, aspect, and overall meaning.

Part 3 – Levels of effectiveness of educational institution administration were analyzed mean () and standard deviation (S.D.). The analysis results obtained were interpreted by item, aspect, and overall meaning.

Part 4 – Transformational leadership affecting effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Education Office was analyzed using multiple regression analysis.

Part 5 – Problems and suggestions about transformational leadership of educational institution administrators and effectiveness of educational institution administration were analyzed to measure frequency.

Part 6 – Guidelines to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, from an interview with administrators, were analyzed using content analysis.

3. Results

According to the study on a guideline to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, the analysis results can be concluded as follow:

1. Most of the respondents are women, aged 26-35 years, graduated with a bachelor's degree, teach in Prathomsuksa classroom, and had 6-10 years teaching experience.
2. Overall transformational leadership level of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office was at a high level. Consideration of each aspect found all aspects were at a high level. The aspect with the highest mean was intellectual stimulation (= 4.08 and S.D.= 0.56) and the aspect with the lowest mean was individualized consideration (= 4.03 and S.D.= 0.66).

Table 1: Levels of transformational leadership of administrators.

No. Administrators' transformational leadership Operational level (n=266)

Condition	M(SD)	LL	UL
Intellectual stimulation	4.10(0.56)	High	1
Inspirational motivation	4.09(0.63)	High	3
Individualized consideration	4.03(0.66)	High	4
Idealized influence	4.10(0.63)	High	2

3. Overall level of effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office was at a high level. Consideration of each aspect found all aspects were at a high level. The aspect with the highest mean was adaptability to internal and external environment (= 4.20 and S.D.= 0.62). The aspect with the lowest mean was eagerness to learn, passion for reading, and students' motivation to seek knowledge (= 3.90 and S.D.= 0.58).

Table2: Levels of effectiveness of educational institution administration.

No. Effectiveness of educational institution administration Operational level (n=266)

Condition	M(SD)	LL	UL
Eagerness to learn, passion for reading, students' motivation to seek knowledge	3.90(0.58)	High	5
Teachers' job satisfaction	4.09(0.63)	High	3
Teachers' ability in using media, innovation, and technologies	4.13(0.53)	High	2
Ability to manage resources efficiently	4.09(0.63)	High	4
Adaptability to internal and external environment	4.20(0.62)	High	1

4. Two aspects of transformational leadership affecting effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office were idealized influence and intellectual stimulation, multiple correlation coefficient was 0.878, being able to mutually predict effectiveness of educational institutional administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office by 77.10% with the statistical significance level of 0.05.

Table 3: Multiple regression analysis results of transformational leadership affecting effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office.

Variables selected into the equation	β	SE.B	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	.905	.113		7.973*	.000
Idealized influence (X ₄)	.555	.045	.668	12.449*	.000
Intellectual stimulation (X ₁)	.221	.050	.239	4.453*	.000

* statistical significance level of 0.05.

5. Analysis results of the open ended questionnaire about problems and suggestion about guidelines to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office can be concluded as follow: With regard to transformational leadership, an academic meeting and training should be held, teachers' operations should be supported and admired, tasks should be assigned in accordance with teachers' abilities, and being a role model administrator. In relation to effectiveness of educational institution administration, students should be promoted to have reading behavior, learn outside classroom, teachers should have ability in using a variety of media and technologies, administrators should allocate a budget in a systematic manner and adapt themselves to new situations regularly.

6. As for guidelines to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators, 2 aspects that are able to improve the effectiveness are intellectual stimulation and idealized influence. Effectiveness of educational institution administration requires strategic planning with PDCA, proactive policies, and advanced technology.

4. Discussion

The research results on guidelines to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office can be discussed as follow:

1. Transformation leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, overall and each aspect, is at a high level, especially intellectual stimulation since most administrators view the importance of global social changes. School personnel should be promoted and supported to have readiness at work. This is consistent with a study conducted by Nilawan Chantarangsi (2022:102) on the relationship between transformational leadership of educational institution administrators and online learning management by teachers in the New Normal, under the Secondary Educational Service Area Office Chanthaburi-Trat, as the study results found overall it was at a high level and consideration of each aspect found all aspects were at a high level. It is consistent with a study conducted by Orawan Puttaradomnoensuk (2021:126) and found that overall and each aspect of transformational leadership of educational institution administrators under Samut Songkhram Primary Educational Service Area Office were at a high level. A study conducted by Angkul Taowan (2019:80) on school administrators' transformational leadership that affects learning organizations under the Secondary Education Service Area Office 17 found that overall and each aspect of transformational leadership were at a high level. Which, difference to authentic leadership that the need for authentic leaders has increased in recent years. Among the most important reasons for this is that the leadership approaches are focused on increasing efficiency and speed in industrial organizations based on mass production in large factories. (Cem Akin. 2022: 344).

2. Effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, overall and each aspect, is at a high level. The aspect with the highest mean is adaptability to internal and external environment. Administrators and teachers provide preparedness to cope with any impact and changes that may arise by considering the possibility of situations. A study conducted by Muhammad Faizal A. Ghani, Saedah Siraj, Norfariza Mohd Radzi, Faisal Elham. (2011 : 1711) on school effectiveness and improvement practices in excellent schools in Malaysia and Brunei found that excellent schools in Malaysia and Brunei have practiced the effective school practices based on school effectiveness and improvement approach at very often and often level respectively. This means that excellent schools are able to adopt the approach of effective school practices because of the existence of cooperation in the process variables that form the structure and culture of the

school. A study conducted by Kanokthip Dokladda (2017:66) on the relationship between educational institution administration and effectiveness of educational institution of Ratwinit Bangkako School under the Secondary Education Service Area Office 6 found the overall relationship is at a high level. On the other hand, resilience as a process seems to embed to an event. Thus, efforts to build resilience must align with the existing context and situation while paying attention to various resources at the individual, organizational, or community level. Moreover, efforts to build resilience need to consider the diversity of perspectives regarding how individuals, organizations, or communities understand and respond to situations and events. At the individual level, inviting individuals to seek personal meaning for what they do has a vital role in building resilience. (Sahala Harahap, Diajeng Herika Hermanu, Tanti Sugiharti, Ruslaini. 2022: 162)

3. Transformational leadership affecting effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office – 3 aspects of transformational leadership affecting the effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office are intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, and idealized influence with the statistical significance level of 0.05. A study conducted by Lakkana Sakkemhan, Pornthep Satiennoppakao, and Walnika Chalabang (2020:Abstract) on transformational leadership of directors affecting work effectiveness of teachers in educational institutions under the Office of Nakhon Phanom Vocational Education Commission found that 2 aspects of transformational leadership affecting work effectiveness of teachers with the statistical significance level of 0.05 were intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration. School administrators with strong self-efficacy beliefs will contribute to creating strong schools with their sustainability leadership skills. Finding a statistically significant relationship between school administrators' self-efficacy beliefs and sustainable leadership characteristics. (Tuba Yavas. 2022: 316)

4. Guidelines to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office – 2 aspects of transformational leadership are intellectual stimulation and idealized influence. Transformational leadership of administrators shall improve effectiveness of educational institution administration, according to the interview with school administrators, by means of 1) Strategic planning with PDCA. Edward Deming (as cited in Witton Simachokdee, 1998 : 84) stated that preparation and planning is to get better understanding of objectives and determine a control topic, goals to achieve, and methods to achieve the set goals, 2) Proactive policies – a study conducted by Achara Niyamapa (2021:181) on a model of new normal school administration to desirable educational quality in changing context concluded that the model of new normal school administration consists of proactive policies, flexible organizational structure, new operating system, reversal curriculum development, contextual learning management, and interdisciplinary assessment, 3) Advanced technologies, consistent with Suwit Hirunyakan (1997:269) giving the meaning of technology as science related to art in applying scientific knowledge for practical purposes, especially in industry.

5. Suggestions: General suggestions

1. Transformational leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, overall and each aspect, is at a high level. Consideration of each aspect found individualized consideration is lower than other aspects Therefore, school administrators should consider teachers increasingly by giving advice, consultation, attention, suggestion, and supporting teachers to express their capabilities to achieve career advancement. The most important thing is to assign tasks that meet the areas they are good at.

2. Effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office, overall and each aspect, is at a high level. However, eagerness to learn, passion for reading, and students' motivation to seek knowledge are lower than other aspects. Therefore, students should be instilled a love of reading, love to read project should be held regularly, reading corners should be provided in school areas to encourage students to seek knowledge from books and printed matters in addition to other media.

3. Transformational leadership affects effectiveness of educational institution administration of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office. It can be seen that there are 3 independent variables for prediction, namely, intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, and idealized influence while inspirational motivation does not affect the effectiveness of educational institution administration. Thus, school administrators should improve and motivate teaches by means of awards, compliments, salary increase when teachers bring good reputation to school.

4. Guidelines to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators of private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office – there is no different opinion from teachers' opinions. Intellectual stimulation and idealized influence can be developed to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration which can solve a gap between teachers and administrators. As for effectiveness of educational institution administration in relation to PDCA strategy, proactive policies, and technologies, administrators should work cooperatively with private agencies and other agencies for sharing information to develop their organizations accordingly.

6. Suggestions for future research

1. Different types of transformational leadership affecting effectiveness of educational institution administration should be studied.
2. Other transformational leadership theories should be studied to synthesize variables that shall affect effectiveness of educational institution administration.
3. Transformational leadership affecting effectiveness of educational institution administration should be studied in other provinces or other agencies to make a comparison and beneficial research results shall be used for education development accordingly.
4. A study should be conducted on a guideline to improve effectiveness of educational institution administration by using transformational leadership of administrators under other affiliations since this study was conducted among private schools under Samut Sakhon Provincial Education Office only and an interview should be conducted with more than 5 administrators in order to obtain various information.

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